

Case study on use of the Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS) economic impact study

Data Archive: UK Data Service

Funder: Economic and Social Research Council

Introduction

The Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS) received additional responsibilities in 2012 and was renamed the UK Data Service. This case study examines how the economic impact study of the ESDS published in 2012 (Beagrie *et al* 2012), has been used in funding advocacy to Government by the UK Data Service and its principal funder the Economic and Social Research Council. It is based on interviews with UK Data Service and research council staff conducted in February 2016.

The ESDS economic impact study is currently the only example of a fully developed quantified economic impact study for social science research data infrastructure.

The case study is therefore likely to be of interest to all social science archives in Europe, their funders in government and national research councils and academies, and other core stakeholders such as data creators and users.

The key economic findings from the ESDS impact study were that the quantifiable benefits significantly exceeded the value of the funding invested in the Service.

5.4 to 1 benefit/cost ratio

There was a 5.4 to 1 benefit/cost ratio of net economic value to the Service's operational costs.

Counter-factual: from 2.5 to 1 up to 10 to 1 returns on investment in data and related infrastructure arising from additional use

A counter-factual approach estimated the increase in return on annual investment in the data and ESDS research data infrastructure services of £58 (€68) million to £233 (€274) million over 30 years (Net Present Value and £/€ exchange rate August 2016).

After Beagrie *et al* 2012.

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How the impact study has been used

The biggest use of the ESDS impact study from the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)'s perspective is in the headline figures and input of these figures into funding bids to Government and more generally in demonstrating the impact and returns on ESRC investments.

The 2012 ESDS economic impact study has been cited by ESRC in many reports and bids.

A lot of the focus when bidding to Government is purely on numbers; easy ones to understand such as how many datasets, users, downloads, and so on. The Impact Study gave figures on Return on Investment, efficiencies, re-use of data, etc. It was (and remains) enormously useful. More generally case studies give further support to the numbers: they give a huge amount of detail that is useful in helping to sustain government funding.

Much of the initial business case for our types of activities may be usefully presented through straight-forward performance indicators like number of datasets, numbers of users, number of downloads, etc. What are used most are short, snappy descriptions and numbers. The ESRC slide from 2015-6 below is an example of use of the ESDS study impact figures: The results of the ESDS study are still proving useful four years from the date of publication.

Economic and Social Research Council

UK Data Service

- ▶ **10x return on investment**
- ▶ Re-use of research data provides:
 - new research opportunities
 - increases productivity
 - saves time and resources for researchers, teachers and policymakers.
- ▶ Increased use of data due to the ESRC-funded UK Data Service is independently estimated to be worth **£58M-£230M** over 30 years from one single year's expenditure

UKDS has:

- over **6,000 datasets**,
- over **25,000 registered users**, **60,000 downloads** worldwide each year.

ESRC 50th Anniversary logo

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This is the only ESRC infrastructure study that has economic impact at its core – although others do include economic elements. At the time of the UK Data Service bid (which succeeded ESDS), this impact study was a key requirement to justify a large capital spend. It may be more difficult to do for other types of investment.

Internally, the UK Data Service has used it as part of the evidence base in discussion with ESRC and there are future plans to produce a follow-up report to provide comparisons.

Many evaluations are metric-driven: an economic evaluation is a synthetic approach that helps provide positive evidence of increased efficiencies and ROI, without having to rely solely on indicators like download numbers. (Download statistics don't measure real use.)

The in-depth ESDS study has helped the UK Data Service to benchmark what success will look like in a few years' time. It is not easy or practical given funding and timescale constraints to undertake such a study in order to provide a benchmark in areas where there is no existing service, but an assessment of the current state of play would be useful in order to demonstrate later what efficiencies have been gained.

Externally, The ESDS economic impact report, particularly the Jisc synthesis of this and two similar studies (Beagrie and Houghton 2014), has already been useful to other countries, so it does have a causal impact internationally in addition to the UK.

Advocacy issues

Defining data infrastructure - all of the contributions that sit around the infrastructure are important. You need to get across what it is (data + staff and skills + technology and governance + professional networks) and what you get back (cost efficiencies, additional research, training, etc.) from the investment in it.

Maturity and scale of the data archive – economic impact often tends to increase over time, so timing and the maturity of archives being studied is an important factor (see CESSDA SaW Return on Investment Factsheet). Also the size of the archive can influence costs through economies of scale and therefore potential returns on investment. For services that are a long way from maturity or scale, we need to identify the individual steps towards the return on investment.

Differences in funding models – are you bidding for a one-off capital sum / project, or recurring core revenue, or a bit of both? The key advocacy points and their relative importance may vary depending on the type of funding model.

Possible differences in funding systems between UK and other European countries - is there a similar capital / revenue funding model divide as in the UK? It seems likely that there might be different systems and that therefore an archive will be bidding against different competitors as well as different disciplines. This might require the arguments used in this case study to be reframed for that national context.

Data archives are very long-term investments that need sustaining and persistent funding- Governments, funding bodies, and the individuals within them, change and the level of understanding of what is required in terms of funding data infrastructure may vary. Its long-term nature and the case for ongoing funding may need to be repeated frequently.

Appreciating rather than depreciating assets - for data infrastructure most of the economic impact is cumulative and realised over an extended period of time: it grows in value over time whereas most infrastructure (such as ships or buildings) has a declining value as it ages. Data becomes more valuable the longer you sustain investment in its collection and as collections and staff expertise grow.

Linked toolkit resources

Benefits Factsheet, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0004>

Effort

Return on Investment Factsheet, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18448/16.0002>

Linked external resources

Beagrie, N., Houghton, J., Palaiologk, A., and Williams, P., 2012, *Economic Impact Evaluation of the Economic and Social Data Service*, <http://www.esrc.ac.uk/files/research/evaluation-and-impact/economic-impact-evaluation-of-the-economic-and-social-data-service/>

Effort

Beagrie, N. and Houghton, J., 2014, *The Value and Impact of Data Sharing and Curation: A synthesis of three recent studies of UK research data centres*, [http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/5568/1/iDF308 - Digital Infrastructure Directions Report%2C Jan14_v1-04.pdf](http://repository.jisc.ac.uk/5568/1/iDF308_-_Digital_Infrastructure_Directions_Report%2C_Jan14_v1-04.pdf)

